

A Detailed Review on Types of lamps and their applications

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ABSTRACT

An electric light is a device that produces visible light by the flow of electric current. It is the most common form of artificial lighting and is necessary to modern society, providing interior lighting for buildings and exterior light for evening and nighttime activities. Types of lamps also have many applications in various sciences. This paper will study the lamps and their applications.

Keywords: Incandescent light bulb, Halogen lamp, LED lamp, Fluorescent lamp, Carbon arc lamp, Discharge lamp .

INTRODUCTION

Before electric lighting became common in the early 20th century, people used oil lamps, gas lights, candles, and fires. Extensive use of electric lighting began with the invention of the first practical incandescent lamp by Thomas Edison and Joseph Swan in the nineteenth century. Since then there have been considerable improvements in lamp efficiency also the different types of lamp. As discussed in the overview, light sources used today can be divided into two main groups: incandescent and luminescent gas discharge lamps. The gaseous discharge type of lamp is either high or low pressure. Low-pressure gaseous discharge sources are the fluorescent and low-pressure sodium lamps. Mercury vapor, metal halide and high-pressure sodium lamps are intended high-pressure gaseous discharge sources. The energy efficiency of electric lighting has increased radically since the premiere arc lamps and the incandescent light bulb of the 19th century. Modern electric light sources come in a profusion of types and sizes adapted to a myriad of applications. Most modern electric lighting is powered by centrally produced electric power, but lighting is also possible to be powered by mobile or standby electric generators or battery systems. Battery-powered lights, usually called flashlights or torches, are used for portability and as backups when the main lights fail. The word "lamp" can refer either to a light source or to the appliance that holds the source. [1]

Incandescent light bulb: Incandescent lamps are often considered the least energy efficient type of electric lighting commonly found in residential buildings. Although inefficient, incandescent lamps possess a number of key advantages—they are inexpensive to buy, turn on instantly, are available in a huge array of sizes and shapes and provide a pleasant, warm light with excellent color rendition. [2]

Types of Incandescent Lamps

There are three common types of incandescent lamps (called A-line lamps) used in residential applications: [3]

- 1- Standard incandescent or pear-shaped A-19 lamps
- 2- Energy-saving or halogen A-19 lamps
- 3- Reflector or parabolic reflector (PAR) lamps, sometimes called "flood" or "spot" lamps

Fig 1: incandescent light bulb diagram

Standard Incandescent A-Line Lamps

Commonly known as the screw-in "A"-type lamp that use a medium Edison (E-26) base, standard incandescent bulbs are the least efficient light source commonly found in homes. These lamps produce visible light by heating a tiny coil or filament of tungsten wire that glows when it is heated by an electrical current. "Long-life" lamps are an example of lamps with thicker, stronger filaments that can last much longer than a standard service lamp, but they are less energy efficient.

New efficiency standards for lighting require lamps to use about 25% less energy. These standards began taking effect starting in January 2012 and the phase-in will be complete as of January 1, 2014, after which time traditional incandescent general service lamps such as the common A-19 will not be available in most stores. Learn more about the new lighting standards. [4]

Energy-Saving Incandescent (or Halogen) Light bulbs

A halogen lamp is a type of incandescent lamp with a capsule that holds a special halogen gas composition around the heated filament to increase the efficacy of the incandescence. They are more energy efficient than standard incandescent bulbs but somewhat more costly. Halogen lamps may also have a special inner coating that reflects heat back into the capsule to further improve efficacy by "recycling" the otherwise wasted heat. Together, the filling and coating recycle heat to keep the filament

hot with less electricity. They also provide excellent color rendition.

Halogens are a little more expensive than standard incandescent lamps, but are less expensive to operate because of their higher efficacy and longer life expectancy. They are commonly used in reflector lamps such as indoor and outdoor flood or spot lighting, indoor recessed and track fixtures, and floor and desk lamps.

Some halogen bulbs are dimmable, as indicated on the package, and are compatible with timers and other lighting controls.

Reflector Lamps

Reflector bulbs (Type R) spread and direct light over specific areas. They are used mainly for floodlighting, spotlighting, and down lighting applications both indoor and outdoor.[5]

There are two types of reflector lamps:

Parabolic aluminized reflector lamps (Type PAR) are used for a number of applications, including outdoor floodlighting.

Ellipsoidal reflector lamps (Type ER) focus light beams about 2 inches in front of its enclosure, projecting light down from recessed fixtures. Ellipsoidal reflectors are twice as energy efficient as parabolic reflectors for recessed fixtures.[6]

Halogen lamp: The halogen lamp is also known as a quartz halogen and tungsten halogen lamp. It is an advanced form of incandescent lamp. The filament is composed of ductile tungsten and located in a gas filled bulb just like a standard tungsten bulb, however the gas in a halogen bulb is at a higher pressure (7-8 ATM). The glass bulb is made of fused quartz, high-silica glass or aluminosilicate. This bulb is stronger than standard glass in order to contain the high pressure. This lamp has been an industry standard for work lights and film/television lighting due to compact size and high lumen output. The halogen lamp is being replaced slowly by the white LED array lamp, miniature HID and fluorescent lamps. Increased efficiency halogens with 30+ lumens per watt may change sale decline in the future.[7]

Fig 2: halogen lamp diagram

Advantages:

- 1- Halogen Lamps are small, lightweight
- 2- Low cost to produce
- 3- Does not use mercury like CFLs(fluorescent) or mercury vapor lights
- 4- Better color temperature than standard tungsten (2800-3400 Kelvin), it is closer to sunlight than the more "orangy" standard tungsten.
- 5- Longer life than a conventional incandescent
- 6- Instant on to full brightness, no warm up time, and it is dimmable

Disadvantages:

- 1- Extremely hot (easily capable of causing severe burns if the lamp is touched).
- 2- The lamp is sensitive to oils left by the human skin, if you touch the bulb with your bare hands the oil left behind will heat up once

the bulb is activated, this oil may cause an imbalance and result in a rupture of the bulb.

3- Explosion, the bulb is capable of blowing and sending hot glass shards outward. A screen or layer of glass on the outside of the lamp can protect users.

4- Not as efficient as HID lamps (Metal Halide and HPS lamps)

How it Works

The halogen lamp has a tungsten filament similar to the standard incandescent lamp; however the lamp is much smaller for the same wattage, and contains a halogen gas in the bulb. The halogen is important in that it stops the blackening and slows the thinning of the tungsten filament. This lengthens the life of the bulb and allows the tungsten to safely reach higher temperatures (therefore makes more light). The bulb must be able to stand higher temperatures so fused quartz is often used instead of normal silica glass. A halogen is a monovalent element which readily forms negative ions. There are 5 halogens: fluorine, chlorine, bromine, iodine, and astatine. Only Iodine and Bromine are used in halogen tungsten lamps.

A.) The lamp is turned on and the filament begins to glow red as more current passes through it. The temperature rapidly increases. The halogens boil to a gas at relatively low temperatures: Iodine (184 C) or Bromine (59 C).

B.) Normally tungsten atoms evaporate off of the filament and deposit on the inside of the bulb, this blackens normal incandescent lamps. As atoms leave the filament the filament gets thinner. Eventually the filament breaks (usually at the ends of the filament). In a halogen tungsten lamp the tungsten atoms chemically unite with the halogen gas molecules and when the halogen cools, the tungsten is redeposit back on the filament. This process is called the halogen cycle.

The halogen bulb comes in two basic configurations: single and double ended. The most common halogen lamps are double ended; these generally are the larger wattage lamps and are used for work lights, yard lights and film production lamps. The halogen lamp has an instant 'on' ability unlike mercury vapor or high pressure sodium; therefore they work well for security lamps that are activated by motion sensors. The life of a halogen lamp is shortened by frequent on and off cycles. [8]

Fluorescent lamp: Fluorescents are a large family of light sources. There are three main types of fluorescent lamps: cold cathode, hot cathode, and electroluminescent. Although there are a large number of lighting options, the majority of lighting in homes is done by either incandescent or fluorescent lights. Fluorescent lighting has a considerable advantage in energy efficiency over incandescent lighting. Fluorescent lights can produce 50-100 lumens/watt compared to about 15 lumens/watt for incandescent bulbs.[7]

Fig 3: compact fluorescent lamp diagram

The familiar geometry of fluorescent lights involves a long narrow glass tube with two electrical connections on each of the metal caps which seal the ends of the tube. The tube is filled with noble gases such as argon, neon or krypton to suppress chemical reactions resulting from the electrical discharges in the tube. According to Bloomfield, these gases are at a pressure of about 0.3% of atmospheric pressure. A few drops of mercury is placed in the tube, and the vapor pressure is sufficient so that something like one in a thousand of the atoms inside the tube is a mercury atom in the gas phase. The properties of these mercury atoms make them very efficient light emitters by fluorescence when they are struck by energetic electrons inside the tube.

If electrons are removed from the mercury atoms by collisions with high speed electrons, they can produce light by emission (see mercury spectrum) when electrons make transitions downward to fill the electron gaps produced. One key to getting light out of the fluorescent tube is then to produce the high speed electrons which can "excite" the mercury atoms so that they will produce light. This is done in most fluorescent tubes by heating a filament in the end of the tube, which frees some electrons. Other types use high voltages to eject electrons from electrodes at the ends. Once freed, the electrons can be accelerated in the tube by the applied AC voltage. Some of the electrons transfer energy to the mercury atoms in collisions, so that one or more of the electrons of the mercury atom is elevated to an excited state. Once the electrical discharge in the tube is started, the current must be controlled to maintain a steady light source. This is done by coil arrangement called a fluorescent light ballast. [7]

The process of producing light from the mercury atoms is fairly efficient, but a large part of it is in the ultraviolet rather than the visible range. The final transition of the electrons to the ground state of the mercury atom produces light at 254 nm, considerably below the blue limit of human vision at about 400 nm. The ultraviolet light does not get through the glass envelope of the tube, but because of its high quantum energy it can be used to advantage in producing visible light. To produce light in the visible range, the inside of the tube is coated with a phosphor powder. When the ultraviolet light strikes the powder, it produces excitations of the electrons of the phosphor which then produce visible light by a process called fluorescence. Ultraviolet photons associated with the 254 nm uv light have quantum energies of 4.9 electron volts, whereas the energy range for the visible photons which we can see is from 1.6 to 3.1 eV. Since there are many intermediate levels for the electrons to drop to after being excited by the uv photons, they can produce visible photons of light throughout the visible range, producing nearly white light.

The production of white light is a challenging undertaking. In the case of the fluorescent lights, a carefully selected and blended set of phosphors is used so that the wavelengths at which it fluoresces are distributed evenly over the visible range. Current fluorescent lighting uses six standard phosphor blends: cool white, deluxe cool white, warm white, deluxe warm white, white, and daylight. The daylight phosphor which was used in early fluorescent lights tips the light toward the blue end and is criticized as being "cold". The "cool" phosphors resemble daylight and are more nearly color neutral, while the "warm" phosphors tip the spectrum toward the red end and resemble incandescent lighting.

The only disadvantage of using compact fluorescent light bulbs is that each bulb has about 5 mg of mercury that may be dangerous to some individuals and may cause serious injuries if inhaled. Other than that, fluorescent light bulbs are good to the

environment as it uses less amount of energy when lit. Even with the light bulb having to give off the same amount of light as a standard incandescent light bulb would, fluorescent light bulbs hold 10 times longer and create 70% less heat so it is safe to use in all conditions.

LED lamp: An LED light bulb is a solid-state lighting (SSL) device that fits in standard screw-in connections but uses LEDs (light-emitting diodes) to produce light. LED light bulbs are a more environmentally-friendly alternative to incandescent bulbs. LED bulbs use a semiconductor device that emits visible light when an electric current passes through it. That property is known as electroluminescence. Compact fluorescents, the most common alternative to incandescent bulbs, use electricity to excite mercury gas until it emits ultraviolet (UV) light. That light is then passed through a phosphor, which causes it to emit more visible light. LEDs themselves have been around for some time, but only recently have improvements in efficiency, cost and output made them viable for the larger-scale lighting used in households, businesses and other environments. Due to the rapid progress in LED technologies, products exist with wide ranges of efficiencies and life spans. The bulbs can work for 50000 hours, if not run outside of the specified temperature range. They use about 8-11 watts of power to replace a 60-watt incandescent with at least 806 lumen and 9.5 watts for a 75-watt equivalent. This capacity provides an efficiency gain of up to 80% over incandescent bulbs.[9]

Fig 4: led lamp diagram

Other benefits of LED light bulbs:

- 1- Cooler than incandescent bulbs in operation.
- 2- Instant on, unlike compact fluorescent bulbs.
- 3- Broad range of color possibilities.
- 4- Customizable lights can be controlled through a Bluetooth connection.
- 5- Lowest cost over ownership of all lights.
- 6- No mercury and minimal toxic materials required.
- 7- A single lamp represents a reduction of hundreds of pounds of CO₂, compared to use of incandescent.
- 8- Possible simultaneous use in data transfer with LiFi.

However there also some caveats. Research indicates that some wavelengths may be damaging to eyes over time. Furthermore, toxic metals are used to produce some wavelengths of lights, which would increase the environmental impact of those particular bulbs.[10]

Enter the LED, or light-emitting diode. LEDs have been around for many years they light up digital clocks, Christmas lights, flashlights and traffic signals, and they tell you when you've got a new voicemail message on your cell phone. But as far as household lighting goes, LEDs have never really taken off. Certain drawbacks have kept companies from manufacturing them in standard, replacement-size light bulb form. In the last few years, though, these LED replacement bulbs, the kind you just screw into a lamp like you do an incandescent bulb, have become much more common -- which is to say a fair number of businesses and a handful of households are using them. In some ways, LED light bulbs are a perfect technology. But they still have a way to go before they become the higher-efficiency bulb of choice. In this article, we'll find out why. We'll look into how they work, why they're a desirable lighting choice, and what will have to change before the rest of us start using them in our bedside lamps.

Carbon arc lamp: The carbon arc lamp was the first widely-used type of electric light and the first commercially successful form of electric lamp. The arc light's development had to coincide with basic power generation developments. As batteries, generators and power conditioning technology developed arc lamps could be made more sophisticated. The carbon rod was often replaced by magnetite (iron ore) for longer life by 1905. The carbon arc lamp led to other arc discharge lamps like the mercury vapor, sodium and fluorescent lamps. Today the lamp has been replaced by the xenon short-arc lamp.[7]

Fig 5: Carbon arc lamp diagram

Advantages:

- 1- Super bright light, capable of lighting a large length of street or a large factory interior
- 2- Was the ONLY electric light available to light large areas from 1800 - 1901
- 3- Was cheaper to light streets with the arc lamp than gas or oil lamps

Disadvantages:

- 1- Carbon rods had to be replaced after a short period of time, this became a full time job in a city
- 2- Produces dangerous UV-A, UV-B, and UV-C rays
- 3- Created a buzzing sound and flickering as the light burned
- 4- Created large amounts of RFI (radio frequency interference)
- 5- Dangerous: it was a fire hazard, many theaters burned as a result of the excessive heat or sparks emitted, also the unenclosed lamp could easily electrocute or severally burn technicians.
- 6- Carbon Monoxide emissions (bad for indoor use!) It only worked in the past because buildings were poorly insulated and fresh air could enter. Some of today's energy efficient buildings are almost air tight.

How it Works:

The lamp is a spark or electric arc through the air between two carbon rods. The rods must have a gap in between of the right size. If the gap is too big then the arc will flicker more or may go out, if the gap is too narrow then it will produce less light.

The first carbon was made of charcoal (made from wood). The carbon substance is vaporized in the high temperature of the arc (around 6500 F, 3600 C). The carbon vapor is highly luminous (very bright) and this is why we use carbon in the lamp. This light is much more useful and bright than that of an arc between steel like in the Jacobs Ladder. The carbon vapor and normal air ionizes easily which helps make light. When the atoms of the carbon and air ionize it means they give up and take on electrons. This happens as electric current passes from one electrode (in this case one of the carbon rods) to the other electrode. Lighting ionizes the air that it passes through.

The carbon arc lamp once lit produces a useful bright light, however undesirable aspects exist. The lamp produces hot sparks and buckyballs which can and have caused fires. Early arc lamps used in department stores were a concern because hot sparks would randomly fall to the floor, on people, or on merchandise. The lamp also produces UV-A, UV-B, and UV-C light which are harmful to both the eyes and skin. Early arc lamp makers didn't know about UV light yet, but did realize that diffusing the light made for better quality light.

Early arc lamp inventors created glass globes to fit around the lamp. Some globes were made of opal glass to diffuse the light and the silica glass blocked some of the harmful UV rays. Early globes often had an open top to allow heat to escape (see the various designs near the bottom of this page here). These protective globes are not to be confused with the "enclosed carbon arc".

The enclosed carbon arc was an arc lamp which completely enclosed the electrodes. The upper electrode was fed through a hole in the top. This enclosed lamp prevented oxygen from easily reaching the arc. With less available oxygen the arc burned slower and the lamp life was greatly improved.

The Mercury Arc: Some early visionaries discovered that by adding mercury into the enclosed arc lamp a green light was created. This was an early predecessor to the mercury vapor lamp. When the hot lamp struck it vaporized the mercury stuck to the inside of the bulb, this helped produce better light with a higher efficiency. The mercury arc was not popular and did not take over the market because it had an ugly greenish color. It did get used as a germicidal lamp due to its increased UV emission. We do not call this a "mercury vapor lamp", the "mercury vapor lamp" as we know today uses a sealed low or high pressure bulb/tube and the two electrodes are made of metal or tungsten, not carbon sticks. We have a separate page for this more advanced type of lamp here. Bucky balls are made of Carbon-20 through 60. Buckyballs are giant molecules which border on being a 'solid' not a small particle. These large molecules behave strangely compared to normal molecules. There are up to 240 electrons total, they act collectively when excited and oscillate back and forth forming a surface plasmon. They are created in natural soot and charcoal which is part of the process of making the carbon rods for the lamp. [11]

Discharge lamp: The use of electrically excited gas discharges significantly predates the invention of the incandescent lamp. Physics labs of yesteryear as well as today have use of a variety of gas filled tubes used for numerous purposes involving light

generation including spectroscopy, materials analysis, studies of gas dynamics, and laser pumping. Look through any scientific supply catalog and you will see many different types of gas filled tubes in all shapes and sizes.

Gas discharge lamps are used in virtually all areas of modern lighting technology including common fluorescent lighting for home and office - and LCD backlights for laptop computers, high intensity discharge lamps for very efficient area lighting, neon and other miniature indicator lamps, germicidal and tanning lamps, neon signs, photographic electronic flashes and strobes, arc lamps for industry and A/V projectors, and many more. Gas discharge automotive headlights are on the way - see the section: "HID automotive headlights".

Because of the unusual appearance of the light from gas discharge tubes, quacks and con artists also have used and are using this technology as part of expensive useless devices for everything from curing cancer to contacting the dead. Unlike incandescent lamps, gas discharge lamps have no filament and do not produce light as a result of something solid getting hot (though heat may be a byproduct). Rather, the atoms or molecules of the gas inside a glass, quartz, or translucent ceramic tube, are ionized by an electric current through the gas or a radio frequency or microwave field in proximity to the tube. This results in the generation of light - usually either visible or ultraviolet (UV). The color depends on both the mixture of gasses or other materials inside the tube as well as the pressure and type and amount of the electric current or RF power. (At the present time, this document only deals with directly excited gas discharge lamps where an AC or DC electric current flows through the gas.)

Fluorescent lamps are a special class of gas discharge lamps where the electric current produces mostly invisible UV light which is turned into visible light by a special phosphor coating on the interior of the tube. The remainder of this document discusses two classes of gas discharge lamps: low pressure 'neon' tubes used in signs and displays and high intensity discharge lamps used for very efficient area and directional lighting.[12]

Safely Working with Gas Discharge Lamps and Fixtures

Fixtures for gas discharge lamps may use up to 30,000 V while starting depending on technology. And, they are often not isolated from the power line. Neon signs are powered by transformers or electronic ballasts producing up to 15,000 V or more. Thus, the only safe way to work with these is to assume that they are potentially lethal and treat them with respect.

HID Gas discharge lamp

Fig 6: Discharge lamp diagram

Hazards include:

- 1- Electric shock. There is usually little need to probe a live fixture. Most problems can be identified by inspection or with an ohmmeter or continuity tester when unplugged.
- 2- Discharge lamps and fixtures using iron ballasts are basically pretty inert when unplugged. Even if there are small capacitors inside the ballast(s) or for RFI prevention, these are not likely to bite. However, you do have to remember to unplug them before touching anything!
- 3- Neon signs using iron transformers are also inert when unpowered - just make sure they are off and unplugged before touching anything!

However, those using electronic ballasts can have some nasty charged capacitors so avoid going inside the ballast module and it won't hurt to check between its outputs with a voltmeter before touching anything. Troubleshooting the electronic ballast module is similar to that of a switch mode power supply. See the document: Notes on the Troubleshooting and Repair of Small Switch mode Power Supplies. The pulse starters of some high intensity discharge lamps may produce up to 30 kV during the starting process. Obviously, contact with this voltage should be avoided keeping in mind that 30 kV can jump over an inch to anyplace it wants!

- 1- Nasty chemicals: Various toxic substances may be present inside high pressure discharge lamps (sodium and mercury) and neon signs (some phosphors). Contact with these substances should be avoided. If a lamp breaks, clean up the mess and dispose of it properly and promptly. Of course, don't go out of your way to get gut on the broken glass! WARNING: Metallic sodium reacts with water to produce hydrogen gas, an explosive. However, it is unlikely that the inner tube of a sodium vapor lamp would break by accident.
- 2- Ultra-Violet (UV) light: High intensity discharge lamps generate substantial UV internally, often the particularly nasty UV-B variety. Unless designed to generate UV (for medicinal purposes, photoengraving, or whatever), the short wave radiation will be blocked by the outer glass envelope and/or phosphor coating. However, should the outer envelope break or be removed, the lamp will still operate (at least for a while - some have a means of disabling themselves after a few hours or less of exposure to air). DO NOT operate such a lamp preferably at all but if you do, at least take appropriate precautions to avoid any exposure to the UV radiation. [13]

Solar Lamp, the Most Eco Friendly Lamp.

A solar lamp is a lamp which is powered by solar energy, a form of portable light fixture consisting of a light-emitting diode (LED), a photovoltaic solar panel, and rechargeable batteries. During the day, the solar panel transforms sunlight into electrical energy, which is stored in the rechargeable batteries. At night, powered by the stored energy, the LED bulb turns on automatically to illuminate. They can be used as both indoor lamps and outdoor lamps. Solar indoor lamps are used for general illumination, while solar outdoor lamps have more function than just illuminating lawn and garden. In many places, those solar lamps are also used in light streets billboards, signs, and parking lots.[14]

Benefits of Solar Lamps:

- 1- Clean energy: using renewable energy, your solar lamp will not create any pollution and emission, as do your electric / conventional lamps. The more you replace your conventional lamps with solar lamps in your home, the more you reduce your household emission.
- 2- No cost to run. There will be no energy cost to run solar lamps.

3- Easy and Low-cost maintenance. Solar lights do not require wiring or other complicated electrical installation. It is a portable fixture, which you can place or move easily where you wish. More than that, once you install a solar light, its LED bulb's can be operated up to 100,000 hours, that is more than 22 years if the lamp is turned on 10 hours every night. Imagine if you use incandescent or fluorescent bulb, how often you will have to replace the bulb during that period.

5- Good investment: Solar lamps payback their retail price in energy savings. As they are durable and long lasting, they will still make bonus after their prices are recovered.

Tips for maximum illumination of Solar Lamps:

Outdoor solar lighting will work in most areas of the United States, however to obtain the maximum illumination of solar lamps take the following tips:

1- The solar collector will absorb the most while the battery capacity will perform best when exposed to direct sunlight. Therefore, place the fixture or solar panel in direct sunlight. Putting a solar lamp in a shaded area may not just cause a lower light output or shorten the illumination duration, but also affect the battery charging, performance and lifetime.

2- A solar lighting system can perform optimal when the solar cells receive the sufficient hours of sunlight recommended by the manufacturer.

3- Occasionally check the battery, clean the dust or dirt on the panel surface, and replace the battery when required.

4- Some solar lighting systems are self-charged units. They need to be placed in a sunny location. Others have the lights separate from a solar cell panel. You need to place just the panel in a sunny location. Choose which type that most suit to your lighting location.

5- During winter, the illumination duration may shorten to be 30% - 50%. Make sure that the solar lighting system has been specifically sized for winter operation.

6- Be sure to choose weather proof, waterproof and shock proof, if you want to buy solar garden lamps or solar lawn lamps.[14]

Closing:

Lots of environmental damage has been caused by the use of non-renewable energy. With increasing interest in fuel conservation and reducing the global warming effects, solar lamps can be a great solution. Solar lights are not only used for illumination purpose, without wires, they appear nicer as decoration than can the wired lamps. Their simple installation makes them easily moved to create new lighting effects. Indeed most manufacturers of solar lamps have produced outdoor fixture solar lights in wide variety of beautiful designs. Combination of beautiful design and soft, subtle accent lighting of solar lamps will give your home and garden a romantic touch; one seen on the above is a sample which is very affordable. [15]

Lamp life expectancy: When purchasing a new light source or replacement bulb, lamp life is a very important consideration. Unfortunately purchasers often do not understand exactly what is meant by "lamp life". There are two very different and distinctive terms that describe life: "rated life" and "economic life". Rated Different types of lights have vastly differing efficiencies and color of light.

average life for metal halide lamps is defined as: A value of lamp life expectancy based on laboratory tests of representative lamps, burning at rated volts, on an approved system, operating with a burning cycle of 10 hours per start. The "average life" is determined when 50% of the lamps initially installed are still operating. Various operating conditions can affect the average life of lamps. One of the most important factors is burning position. Position-oriented lamps (designed to burn in a certain position) are tested and rated based on their designated position. Burning these lamps in other positions can dramatically shorten life, lumen output, and color. Universal lamps can be burned in any position, but as a result, they sacrifice life expectancy and lumen output in some operating positions. Published "rated life" for universal lamps are based on the lamps being burned in the vertical position. "Rated life" for lamps burned in the horizontal position is 75% of the published rating for the vertical application. Lamps, like most electromechanical devices, have a shorter life the more they are turned on and off. Other factors can also affect lamp life, such as high or low operating voltages, marginally operating control devices (ballasts, capacitors, etc.), extremely high operating temperatures, among other conditions. Combinations of these factors can multiply the reduction in "rated life".[16]

Economic Life

"Economic life" is a much better description of actual lamp life than rated life. It refers to the hours of operation a lamp is designed to provide in terms of optimum light output, aesthetic quality, and economic energy consumption. The "economic life" of lamps is generally defined as 60% of the lamp's rated life.

"Rated life does not account for the lumen depreciation, color shifting, and loss in efficacy that always occur as lamps age. To consistently provide a quality lighting system, you must not only consider the lamps that fail, but the lamps that continue to operate. Lower light output (lumen depreciation) occurs even though the lighting system continues to consume the same (or sometimes slightly more) electricity. See the section on light output for more information.

The color of light (CCT) that lamps generate also changes or "shifts" with age. This is rarely noticed during the "economic life" of lamps but often creates problems in the last 40% of "rated life" when color shift may accelerate. During this period more spot replacements are needed for failed lamps. The original lamps often appear to be a different color than the newly installed replacements in almost any case, the cost of a lamp is the smallest fraction (typically 5%) of maintaining a lighting system compared to the energy usage and the labor cost involved in spot relamping. Though "economic life" is the most important factor when considering lamp life, the lamp data tables contain the lamps' "rated life because: 1) it is a means of comparison - other lamp manufacturers only discuss "rated life" and 2) "economic life" is a percentage (generally 60%) of "rated life".[17]

Types of electric lighting include, Incandescent light bulbs, Arc lamps, Gas-discharge lamps, e.g., fluorescent lights and compact fluorescent lamps, neon lamps, flood lamps, modern photographic flashes, Lasers, Light-emitting diodes, including OLEDs and Sulfur lamps.

Name	Optical spectrum	Nominal efficiency (lm/W)	Lifetime (MTTF) (hours)	Color temperature (kelvin)	Color	Color rendering index
Incandescent light bulb	Continuous	4-17	2-20000	2400-3400	Warm white (yellowish)	100

Halogen lamp	Continuous	16-23	3000-6000	3200	Warm white (yellowish)	100
Fluorescent lamp	Mercury line + Phosphor	52-100 (white)	8000-20000	2700-5000*	White (various color temperatures), as well as saturated colors available	15-85
Metal halide lamp	Quasi-continuous	50-115	6000-20000	3000-4500	Cold white	65-93
Sulfur lamp	Continuous	80-110	15000-20000	6000	Pale green	79
High pressure sodium	Broadband	55-140	10000-40000	1800-2200*	Pinkish orange	0-70
Low pressure sodium	Narrow line	100-200	18000-20000	1800*	Yellow, no color rendering	0
Light-emitting diode	Line plus phosphor	10-110 (white)	50,000-100,000	Various white from 2700 to 6000*	Various color temperatures, as well as saturated colors	70-85 (white)
Induction Lamp (External Coil)	Mercury line + Phosphor	70-90 (white)	80,000-100,000	Various white from 2700 to 6000*	Various color temperatures, as well as saturated colors	70-85 (white)

CONCLUSION:

According to the needs of society as well as a variety of lighting and lamps in various sciences, this paper examines the advantages and disadvantages and a short description of the types of light bulbs there. In some cases, energy consumption, environmental impact and the effect of light intensity and light the lamps on the human body health is examined.

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